

Studies on Some N-Acyl N-Phenylhydroxylamines as Metal Complexing Ligands. Part VII. N-o-Tolyl-N-Hydroxysuccinamic Acid

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A new hydroxamic acid—N-o-tolyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid ($R_t^oH_2$) has been prepared and found to act as a complexing ligand. Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of the ligand are isolated as $Cu(R_t^o)(H_2O)_2$ and $Ni(R_t^o)(H_2O)_2$. Their magnetic data, d-d spectra in mull and i.r. spectra in KBr matrix are recorded. From the spectral study of Fe(III)- $R_t^oH_2$ system in aqueous solution, the formation of two different complexes of composition (1 : 1) and (2 : 3) at pH values ≈ 2.00 and ≈ 3.10 has been observed.

IN continuation of our work¹ with N-phenyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid, N-o-tolyl-N-hydroxysuccinamic acid ($R_t^oH_2$) has been synthesised to study the effect of substitution of the phenyl group. It also forms complex compounds with Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), V(V) and U(IV). In the solid state Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes are isolated as $Cu(R_t^o)(H_2O)_2$ and $Ni(R_t^o)(H_2O)_2$.

The ligand $R_t^oH_2$ forms different complexes with Fe(III) at different pH values as observed from the spectral studies of Fe(III)- $R_t^oH_2$ system in aqueous solution. Their compositions have been determined by Job's method of continuous variation².

Experimental

N-o-Tolyl-N-hydroxysuccinamic acid was prepared by condensing succinic anhydride with excess of N-o-tolylhydroxylamine³ in ice cold ether solution containing 10% dry pyridine. The compound was crystallised from aqueous ethanol. It is a white

crystalline solid—m.p. 150° and is soluble in ethanol, acetone, ether and moderately so in water. Solubility in water is 0.85 g per 100 ml of its saturated solution. Its aqueous solution is much more stable than that of N-phenyl-N-hydroxysuccinamic acid. Found: Equivalent wt., 222; C, 59.25; H, 5.90; N, 6.07; $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N$ requires Equivalent wt., 223; C, 59.19; H, 5.83; N, 6.28%. Electronic spectral data: $R_t^oH_2$ — $\lambda_{max}^{aq} = 213$ nm, $\log \epsilon = 3.89$; R_t^oHNa — $\lambda_{max}^{aq} = 213.6$ nm, $\log \epsilon = 3.79$.

Complex compounds of Cu(II) and Ni(II) were prepared. Analytical data are stated in Table 1. They are insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, DMF etc. Their magnetic susceptibility measurements were made and the magnetic moment data are recorded in Table 1. Their d-d spectrum in mull were studied and the results are stated also in Table 1.

The infrared spectral measurements of $R_t^oH_2$, $Cu(R_t^o)(H_2O)_2$ and $Ni(R_t^o)(H_2O)_2$ in KBr matrix were done and the probable assignments^{4,5} of some important vibrations are recorded in Table 2.

Fe(III) complex of the ligand $R_t^oH_2$ forms a brilliant red coloured aqueous solution, the composition of which was determined by Job's method of continuous variation at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) by

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND SPECTRAL DATA OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	%Metal Found (Calc.)	%Nitrogen Found (Calc.)	μ_{eff}	Temp. °K	λ_{max}^{mull} in nm	O.D. in arbitrary Unit
$Cu(R_t^o)(H_2O)_2$	bright green	19.42 (19.80)	4.45 (4.37)	1.90	295	630	0.486
$Ni(R_t^o)(H_2O)_2$	light green	18.06 (18.50)	4.38 (4.41)	2.99	294	390	0.914

TABLE 2. I.R. SPECTRAL DATA OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) COMPLEX AND LIGAND $R_f^oH_2$

$R_f^oH_2$	Cu(R_f^o)(H_2O) ₂	Ni(R_f^o)(H_2O) ₂	Assignments (Probable)
...	3390 (sh.m.)	3390 (b.w.)	H-bonded water molecule
3200 (sp.st.)	O-H stretching vibration
1717 (sp.st.)	due to -COOH
...	1613 (sh.st.)	1620 (sp.st.)	COO ⁻ antisymmetrical stretching.
1653 (sp.st.)	1587 (sp.st.)	1603 (sp.st.)	C = O stretching (tertiary amide)
...	1557 (sh.w.)	1538 (sh.w.)	due to lattice/co-ordinated water
...	1403 (sp.st.)	1408 (b.st.)	COO ⁻ symmetrical stretching
941 (b.m.)	1010 (sp.st.)	1010 (sp.st.)	N-O stretching vibration.

sp = sharp, b = broad, sh = shoulder, st = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

adding requisite amount of $NaClO_4$. First spectral curves were drawn at different pH values (Fig. 1). From the curves wavelengths 480 nm and 470 nm were chosen to study the composition by Job's method at $pH \approx 2.0$ and ≈ 3.1 .

Fig. 1. Spectral curves for Fe(III) chelates. I, $pH = 2.07$; II, $pH = 2.14$; III, $pH = 2.64$; IV, $pH = 2.86$; V, $pH = 3.1$.

The experiment was carried out using A.R. quality reagents, a spectrophotometer (Hilger's UVISPEK) with 1 cm. quartz cell against water as blank, adjusting pH with a Cambridge pH -meter (portable type)

Discussion

The Cu(II) and Ni(II) compounds of the ligand have (1 : 1) composition indicated by analytical data. Their magnetic moments were found to be 1.90 BM and 2.99 BM respectively. The magnetic data indicate that the former has a square planar or distorted octahedral configuration⁶ and the latter should be high spin octahedral complex⁷. The square planar or highly distorted octahedral structure for Cu(II) compound is also supported by the mull spectra which shows absorption maxima at 630 nm, the value lies in the characteristic bands at 900-600 nm of such Cu(II) complexes⁷. The electronic spectra

of Ni(II) complex shows a d-d band at 390 nm, which may be assigned to the allowed transition $^3A_{2g}$ to $^3T_{1g}$ (P) for octahedral Ni(II) complexes⁸.

In aqueous solutions the characteristic band around 213 nm of the ligand $R_f^oH_2$ and its sodium salt R_f^oHNNa is assigned as benzene bands^{9,10}.

I.R. data suggest that there exist the same type of bonding of ligand to Cu(II) and Ni(II), as has been found in the Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes of N-phenyl-N-hydroxysuccinamic acid¹. In addition to bidentate chelating properties of hydroxamic acid^{11,12}

the presence of $\begin{matrix} O-M \\ \diagup \\ C \\ \diagdown \\ O \end{matrix}$ bonding¹³ is also indicated.

Thus the ligand $R_f^oH_2$ appears to behave as a biprotic tridentate one in these complexes.

By Job's method of continuous variation the existence of two different complexes of Fe(III) and $R_f^oH_2$ has been indicated. The purple complex (1 : 1) at $\lambda = 480$ nm and $pH \approx 2.00$ and the red complex (2 : 3) at $\lambda = 470$ nm and $pH \approx 3.10$, have been observed.

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References

- N. N. GHOSH and S. K. MUKHOPADHYAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, ...
- P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
- A. K. MAJUMDAR and G. DAS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1964, **31**, 147.
- D. H. WILLIAMS and I. FLEMING, *Spectroscopic method in Organic Chemistry*, McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., New York, 1966.
- K. NAKAMOTO, *Infrared spectra of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compounds*, Wiley, New York, 1963.

6. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, Chemistry of metal chelate compounds, McGraw Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., New York, 1966.
7. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, Advanced Inorganic Chemistry, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1966.
8. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, Modern Co-ordination Chemistry, Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1960.
9. P. BLADON, Ultraviolet and visible spectroscopy, J. C. P. Schwarz; Physical methods in Organic Chemistry, Oliver and Boyd, London, 1967, p. 146.
10. L. DOUB and J. M. VANDENBELT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **89**, 2714; 1949, **71**, 2414.
11. A. T. PILIPENKO, E. A. SHPAK and L. L. SHEVEHENKO, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1967, **12**, 463-72 (Russ.); *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, **66**, 120345a.
12. D. R. AGRAWAL and S. G. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 571.
13. C. A. MCAULIFFE and W. D. PERRY, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, **683**.